

Effect of Predict-Observe-Explain Strategy on Secondary School Physics Students' Achievement in Simple Harmonic Motion Concept in Ogun State, Nigeria

ADEPOJU, Temitope Matthew, Ph.D

Department of Science Education
Lead City University, Ibadan, Oyo State

tadepoju@ymail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17072813>

Abstract

Students' achievement in Physics in external examination had dwindled over the years. The problem of poor performance in Physics sometimes had not been limited to the students alone but also to teachers' pedagogical strategies. The study examined effect of Predict-Observe-Explain strategy on secondary school Physics students' achievement in Simple Harmonic Motion concept in Ogun State. One hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 levels of significance. The study adopted pretest- posttest control group quasi-experimental design. A total of 166 SS2 Physics students in three senior secondary school intact classes in Ogun State participated in the study. Physics Achievement Test (PAT) with 30 multiple-choice questions ($r=0.81$), was used for data collection. Data were analyzed with descriptive (frequency and percentage) and inferential statistics (ANCOVA). There was a significant effect of Predict-Observe-Explain strategy on students' achievement in Simple Harmonic Motion ($F_{(1,128)}=682.814$, $p<0.05$, partial $\eta^2=0.842$). Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that Physics teachers should adopt Predict-Observe-Explain strategy to teach Physics in secondary schools

Keywords: Predict-Observe-Explain, Physics, Achievement, Simple Harmonic Motion

Introduction

Science is primarily designed to transform the environment towards improving the general quality of life, thus making the world a better place. It is the foundation on which contemporary technological breakthroughs and advancement rest. Science employs observation, experimentation, measurement, and recording to methodically investigate the properties of materials and the behavior of the physical universe (Thomas, 2021). Science is considered to be a systematic, precise, and objective way to study the natural world (Arziqulogli & Iixomovich, 2022). Physics, Chemistry, Mathematics, and Biology constitute the fundamental disciplines of science (Selin & Kaya, 2020).

In recent times, countries all over the world, especially developing ones like Nigeria, are striving hard to develop scientifically and technologically, since the world is a scientific and technological global village where all proper functioning of lives largely depends on science. Without the application of science, it would have been difficult for a human being to explore the other planets of the universe. The development of any society is based on its technological level, and Physics education is a significant factor in enhancing technology development. Physics is known as the study of the nature and characteristics of matter and energy. The pure science of Physics has enormous effects on the modern and globalized society. The science of observing the environment around us is called Physics (Al-Khalili, 2020). Physics is a core subject in science and technology since it studies the essence of natural phenomena and helps people understand the rapidly technological changing society (Edoja & Gbadamosi, 2020).

Physics is the natural development of experiments, observations, and theories to explain the fundamental structure of all we perceive which is crucial for effective living in this jet age of science and technology (Novitra, 2021). Being fundamentally, the study of various forms of energy interactions and inter-conversions with matter, Physics is the study of the nature of our environment and how different energies of nature can be produced, conserved, and changed to another form (Gulbin & Topsakal, 2021). It has been noted that teaching Physics in secondary education involves imparting the fundamental knowledge and concepts of science, helping students develop the skills and abilities necessary to participate in scientific processes, and instilling in them a positive attitude towards and appreciation for science and its applications (Darmaji, Kurniawan & Irdianti, 2019). Physics is a critical subject for effective living in the scientific and technological age, according to the Nigerian Federal Ministry of Education (Agbele, Oyelade & Oluwatuyi, 2020). This implies that all students must be afforded the chance to learn certain Physics ideas, theories, concepts, and abilities. The goals of Physics education, as stated in the new Senior Secondary School Physics Curriculum, provide a clear explanation of these ideas, theories, and skills (Soechoarto, Csapo, Sarimanah, Dervi & Sabri, 2019).

The subject is one of the oldest disciplines and was formally part of natural Philosophy during the scientific revolution period. It has emerged as a unique research subject with new ideas which explain the fundamental mechanics of other sciences and open new avenues for research in other Science areas and Mathematics. The goals of Physics education are to cultivate and improve creativity, provide a foundational understanding of Physics for living in society, prepare students for higher education by teaching them the fundamental theories and principles of Physics, and equip them with the necessary scientific knowledge and mindset for using physics in technology (Usman, Simvyap & Fasanya, 2019). Reaching these goals is crucial, and it calls for a teacher who employs learner-centered teaching strategies since learning occurs when students are actively engaged in the teaching and learning process. Therefore, the difficulties a teacher faces are in creating meaningful instruction that will result in meaningful learning (Kilipamwambu, 2021).

The economic potential of developed nations rests squarely on their advancement in science and technology and Physics played a major role in that aspect. Physics is one of the elective subjects in the Key Learning Area (KLA) of science education (Acosta, 2020). It is for functional living in society, in which students are trained in the art of finding a physical explanation for what they experience, while also having opportunities to experience the scientific methods that can be applied when making critical investigations. The Physics curriculum serves as a continuation of the science where Senior Secondary one to three (SS1-3) curriculum builds on the strength of the current Physics curriculum. Every student is given an opportunity to acquire some of its concepts, principles, and skills. Physics education is expected to develop student's world view in terms of linking reality, putting in personal effort in the enriching learning environment, and constructing their own understanding from the available resource material.

Physics indeed is the pillar of technological and scientific development of most developed nations in the world, for example, improved knowledge of electromagnetism and nuclear Physics led to the inventions of television, the computer, and nuclear materials such as domestic appliances and nuclear weapons. Advances in thermodynamics led to the development of industries while the development in calculus was based on the advances in Mechanics. Thus, there is a need for technically literate citizens with complex problem-solving skills for the

purpose of taking wise decisions and understanding the challenges that might occur in the nearest future. The laws, principles, and theories of Physics are being applied in solving many problems of human beings on earth. It was pointed out that Physics is the heart of science and a pillar of all technological activities (Gulejova & IPPOG, 2021).

Many developed nations like the USA, Japan, France, China, and Russia attained their positions of world power as a result of development in science and technology and Physics played a key role in that direction. The discipline has proven its benefits to mankind as almost every human activity and virtually every profession involves some elements of Physics (Kane & Gelman, 2020). Agronomy, Engineering, Geophysics, Biophysics, Material Sciences, Nuclear Physics, Medicine, and Communication Technology are just a few of the disciplines that rely on the fundamentals of Physics (Falode, Francis, Micheal & Dennis, 2020). The field of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has greatly benefited from the application of Physics concepts. Devices like computers, iPads, smartphones, and satellites have made the globe smaller by enabling communication between people across vast distances. The significance of Mechanics topics in Physics was highlighted by the Senior Secondary School Examination of the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) and the National Examination Council (NECO), which showed that over thirty percent of the questions on the Senior Secondary School Physics examination were related to Mechanics. The areas where students performed poorly in Physics were primarily the Elasticity Properties of Solid, Kinetic Theory, Simple Harmonic Motion, Projectiles Motion, the Relative Density of a solid, Properties of Matter, Equilibrium of forces and Mechanical Energy, simple mathematical computation, and the interpretation of expressions and equations (Edoja & Gbadamosi, 2020, WAEC, 2019). Simple Harmonic Motion (SHM) is a topic in Physics which consists of content knowledge and calculation. The sub content includes period, frequency and amplitude of Simple Harmonic Motion, relationship between Simple Harmonic Motion and circular motion, speed and acceleration of Simple Harmonic Motion, relationship between linear acceleration and angular velocity, energy of Simple Harmonic Motion, free vibration, damped vibration, force vibration and resonance. Effective understanding of Simple Harmonic Motion entails that the theoretical presentations, practical presentations and calculations should be understood by the students. It was stressed that; the cardinal principle of teaching is that the whole is greater than the sum of its part (Knapp, 2019). Simple Harmonic Motion is a perceived difficult concept for students to understand because it often involves a complex equation (Akbar & Budiarti, 2021). Students shy away from mathematical analysis of the concept, which includes period, frequency, amplitude, velocity, and acceleration of Simple Harmonic Motion (Akbar & Budiarti, 2021).

Simple Harmonic Motion can be observed using a spring and a simple pendulum. This motion is a type of periodic motion or oscillation motion where the restoring force is directly proportional to the displacement and acts in the direction opposite to the displacement (Pacela, 2023). The spring that is stretched or compressed around the equilibrium position is proportional to the force applied by force following Hooke's law. The following were observed as candidates' weaknesses as regards Simple Harmonic Motion; poor mathematical representation, inability to accurately give the statement of definitions, state equations, formulas, and substitution to draw conclusion (Umam & Sukarmin, 2020). However, despite the relevance of Physics to the scientific and technological breakthroughs of nations, the subject has been faced with a myriad of problems in Nigeria.

Several studies have revealed that the performance of Nigerian students in secondary school Physics is generally and consistently poor over the years (Assem, Nartey, Appiah & Aidoo, 2023). Numerous causes have been attributed to the low academic performance of science students. The general low academic achievement of students in Physics can be attributed to various factors such as inadequate laboratory facilities, insufficient teaching and learning resources compared to the continuously growing student population, and the incapacity of Physics teachers to impart clear and concise knowledge to their students (Ocheni, 2020). Students' performance in Senior Secondary School examinations is hampered by the poor state of laboratory facilities and the inadequate use of instructional materials (Ali, 2023). The conventional method of teaching that is commonly used does not support the development of skills, objectivity, or critical thinking abilities that will enable the student to function well in society.

The reports of West African Examination Council (WAEC) on the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination, (SSCE) from 2015 to 2019 on students' performances revealed that between 30% and 60% of candidates passed Physics at credit level out of 1,064,384 that sat for the examination in the 5-year period in Nigeria (WAEC, 2015-2019). Simple Harmonic Motion is one of the most topics in Physics at the senior secondary school level in which learners perceived difficult despite being essential for the understanding of other topics (Hartanto, Santoso & Frianto, 2024). One of the main barriers that students encountered in understanding Physics concepts is misconceptions which they had about the concepts. Many studies persistently report of the poor performance of students in Physics especially in the area of Simple Harmonic Motion call for urgent attention (Busari, 2023). This challenging situation has been attributed to a whole number of factors such as students' attitude, poor study habits, the learners' interest in the subject, the learners' self-concept, gender and the teaching method (Marx, Leonhardt & Bergher, 2023). Research findings in the last decades revealed that students commonly lack a deep conceptual understanding of the key ideas regarding the concept of Simple Harmonic Motion and often fail to integrate their mental models into a coherent conceptual framework (Bastos, Sales & Monteiro, 2021). Effective teaching method employed by the teacher is the major contributory factor that influences learners understanding of concept of Simple Harmonic Motion (Roger, 2020). A teaching strategy therefore is the way a lesson is approach that will be used to achieve a set of given objectives. If proper choice of strategy is made and the plan well executed students will actively engage in the lesson and derive benefits immediately (Pacala, 2023). There are varieties of teaching strategies from which a teacher can select for teaching and learning of Physics concepts, but the method employed will depend on a number of variables such as: age of the students, their learning styles, the cognitive level, subject matter, availability of instructional materials and environmental variables among others. Two or more teaching methods can be employed within a lesson content delivery for effective teaching to take place.

Achievement implies something that somebody has done successfully especially using his/her own efforts and skills (Ne & An, 2020). Achievement is the act of obtaining a result through efforts in the quality and quantity of students' work. On the other hand, academic achievement is a measure of knowledge gained through education process usually indicated by test scores, grade point average and degree (Engin, 2020). This is why some schools define this as a certain grade point average (GPA), or ranking in class. Academic achievement can be defined as performance of students in schools (Adonu, Nwagbo, Ugwuanyi & Okeke, 2021). It could be getting high grades and a high GPA level. This high GPA level may be achieved through

the use of innovative teaching strategies. In this regard, the use of innovative teaching strategies may help students to develop better understanding of a subject such as Physics which may lead to improved performance in achievement (Mao, Cai, He, Chen & Fan, 2021).

Science lessons should be designed to provide students the freedom to experiment and engage in group discussions as they attempt to make sense of assignments and tackle difficult challenges. By making lessons engaging, student-centered, and interactive, activity-based and student-centered teaching practices can draw in and hold the attention of students in Physics classes. The Predict-Observe-Explain instructional strategy (POEIS) and the Virtual Laboratory instructional strategy (VLIS), which are being investigated in this study, are two of these activity-based, student-centered instructional strategies. The theory of practical activities, which emphasizes learning by doing, is the foundation of the Predict-Observe-Explain instructional strategy. Predict, Observe and Explain are the three tasks that students complete in this instance. Constructivist learning theory provides the theoretical framework upon which this study is based. The constructivist theory was proposed by Bruner, in 1960 to describe the active nature of learning. Constructivist is a model used to explain how people acquire knowledge. To explain constructivist learning theory, three key principles were identified as: personal experience, active learning and social interactions (Efgivia, Adora, Suriyam, Maulana & Budiarjo, 2021).

- **Personal Experience**

The belief is that learners construct knowledge based on experiences they have encountered in the real world. Learners are actively creating and modifying thoughts, ideas and understanding based on their experiences (Efgivia, Adora, Suriyam, Maulana & Budiarjo, 2021). Knowledge does not look the same for every individual. It is unique and exists in a variety of formats. To foster this type of learning environment, teachers that utilize constructivist design theory present students with problems and activities that are relevant and meaningful to them

- **Active Learning**

In an active learning environment, learners are more than passive recipients of information. Learners are actively engaged in their learning by solving problems and analyzing complex questions (Efgivia, Adora, Suriyam, Maulana & Budiarjo, 2021). Often times, the phrase “learning by doing” is associated with this type of learning environment (Kieuoanh & Hongnhung, 2022). Teachers create active learning environments by employing instructional models such as cognitive apprenticeship and project-based learning (Kieuoanh & Hongnhung, 2022). In addition, because the active learning activities that learners engage in are grounded in realistic and relevant contexts, assessments reflect that, instead of focusing on rote memorization techniques often associated with standardized tests, authentic assessments are often used.

Student achievement is directly correlated with the teaching strategies used in the classroom; therefore, if the subject matter is taught using the most appropriate method, it is likely that students will likewise demonstrate a high level of success in the learning area (Duygu & Halil, 2020). The POEI strategy has proven to be highly effective in science education due to its emphasis on hands-on learning. This approach encourages students to actively engage in investigations and develop their own understanding of scientific concepts (Pulana, 2022). Additionally, it is considered a suitable instrument for exploring students' initial thoughts or existing notions (Arslan & Irfan, 2020). The effectiveness of the conducted studies in reducing students' misunderstandings in chemistry has been confirmed (Yulianti, Suhandi & Sopandi, 2020).

Additional research has demonstrated the positive impact of the POE strategy on students' academic success in science (Kurniawan, Rahayu, Fajaroh & Almunasher, 2020). For example, a study focused specifically on the Chemistry achievement of secondary school students found that the implementation of the POE strategy resulted in improved outcomes (Erdem & Uyanik, 2022). The effectiveness of the POE strategy in promoting student engagement and facilitating classroom discussions is well-documented in the study (Adebayo & Olufunke, 2015). This confirms its positive impact on enhancing practical skills in Basic Science among elementary students. The research carried out has confirmed the success of using the POE approach to enhance the abilities and engagement of aspiring science teachers when it comes to conducting experiments in the laboratories (Barut & Cibik, 2022).

A recent Physics study found that implementing the POE strategy resulted in enhanced student interest and achievement in the subject (Venida & Sigma, 2020). Based on the study, elementary school children's academic performance and attitude toward science are improved when this technique is used (Ramdayami, Latifah, Yurniwati & Taofik, 2023). These include the research that demonstrated the value of metacognition in science achievement through the Predict-Explain-Observe-Explain Approach (PEOE) and the study that validated the efficacy of the Predict-Observe-Explain-Explore Strategy (POEE) in general Chemistry instruction (Dennis & Somerville, 2022).

The POE strategy was found to improve students' academic performance and attitude towards Physics in a study (Sidik, Mulyaningsih & Astuti, 2021). In this study, a quasi-experimental research design was employed to assess how the POE Strategy influenced students' achievement and attitude in Physics. This study involved the participation of 59 seventh-grade students from two intact heterogeneous classes. The control group was taught using the engage-explore-explain-elaborate-evaluate (5E's) learning cycle, while the experimental group was taught using the POE strategy. The t-test method was employed to identify any notable disparities in achievement and attitude between the two groups, as well as within each individual group. The study revealed indicated a notable disparity in the posttest achievement scores between the two groups. The findings indicated that the participants in the experimental group showed superior performance in the posttest compared to those in the control group. Additionally, the experimental group experienced a notable shift in their attitude towards Physics, transitioning from a neutral perspective to a positive one. In contrast, the control group maintained a neutral attitude throughout the study.

Another research was conducted to examine how the Predict-Observe-Explain and Virtual Laboratory Instructional Strategies impact students' performance in Physics practical (Ojo & Owolabi, 2020). The research utilized a quasi-experimental approach, specifically the pretest posttest and control group design. The participants consisted of 74 Physics students in their second year of Senior Secondary school. These students were chosen randomly from three co-educational schools in Osun State, using a multistage procedure. The schools were chosen at random to form two experimental groups and one control group. The participants in the experimental groups were subjected to the Predict-Observe-Explain and Virtual Laboratory Instructional Strategies, whereas the control group received instruction through the traditional laboratory approach. In order to gather pertinent information for this study, the researchers employed the Physics Practical Test (PPT) as their instrument. The PPT involved a practical examination with two simultaneous tests, namely alternative A and alternative B. The hypotheses put forth were examined using various statistical methods, such as, Analysis of Covariance

(ANCOVA), Scheffe Post Hoc Analysis, and Multiple Classification Analysis (MCA). The study's results revealed a noticeable impact on the average scores of students' performance in all three groups, indicating a significant teaching effect.

The effects of the Predict-Observe-Explain instructional strategy on students' practical skills in Physics were investigated in another study (Ojo & Owolabi, 2021). For the research, the study utilized a pretest posttest quasi-experimental design. The study involved a sample of 213 SS II Physics students from six senior secondary schools in Ibadan, Nigeria. The Predict-Observe-Explain instruction yielded better results (adjusted mean = 33.37) compared to the traditional practical instruction (adjusted mean = 24.42).

Statement of the Problem

The performance of Nigerian secondary school students in Physics has not been encouraging. Despite the need for Physics education due to the desire for technological advancement, students' academic performance in the subject is consistently low. Students' low performance in Physics can be attributed to a wide range of factors, such as the use of inappropriate teaching methods by teachers, inadequate laboratory facilities, poorly planned laboratory activities, low student and teacher commitment to the laboratory, partial or complete lack of a laboratory, a shortage of qualified Physics teachers, and the type of laboratory activities used in Physics Laboratory. Studies have established that in conducting laboratory activities, teachers are using mainly teacher-centered approaches.

The National Policy on Education stated goals for Physics education in Nigerian secondary schools are sometimes cast in doubt due to the unsuitable teaching strategies employed by Physics teachers in secondary schools. The majority of teaching strategies, including lecture and demonstration, which are employed in Physics classes and laboratories, encourage memorization and deprive students of the chance to work with materials and think back on their actions as they are being taught and learning. Concretizing learning may be greatly aided by the interactions between students during practical laboratory exercises. It is against this background that, the study determined the effect of Predict-Observe-Explain Instructional strategy on secondary school Physics students' achievement in Simple Harmonic Motion in Ogun State, Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study is to determine the effect of Predict-Observe-Explain strategy on secondary school Physics students' achievement in Simple Harmonic Motion in Ogun State.

Hypothesis

There is no significant main effect of Predict-Observe-Explain strategy on students' achievement in Simple Harmonic Motion in Physics in secondary school in Ogun State

Methodology

The study adopted the pretest- posttest control group quasi-experimental design. The target population for this study was all the SSII students offering Physics in public schools of Ogun Central Senatorial district of Ogun State, Nigeria. This comprised all the senior secondary schools that exist in the six (6) Local Government Areas. There are about 21,694 students (10,687 males and 11,007 females) in SSI in the Senatorial district and 67 senior secondary schools in the area. The reason for choosing SS2 for the study was because the students have attained some

level of adequate knowledge of Physics concepts which are mostly in SSII scheme of work, and they do not have any external examination that could easily distract their desirable active participation. The sample consisted of only two public Senior Secondary schools which are government owned (for the purpose of uniform standard) and which offer Physics up to the Senior Secondary School Certificate (SSSC) level, using multi-stage sampling procedure.

Stage one: Two LGAs were selected through simple random techniques, where all the LGAS were given numbers and three were selected randomly.

Stage two: One school among those that meet inclusive criteria was also chosen through purposeful sampling technique.

Stage three: In each of the selected schools, one intact class was selected through random technique if such school had more than one intact class. In each of the selected schools, the Physics teacher teaching the intact class was chosen as research assistant. Altogether, two research assistants were enlisted and the total number of students was 166 Physics students. The schools selected for the study are public co-educational school with good number of male and female students. This consisted of (70) males and (96) females having the mean age of 15-16 years and the range was 12-17 years and above constituted the sample for the study.

The following instruments were used for the study: Physics Achievement Test (PAT) and Teachers' Instructional Guides (TIG). The PAT instrument consisted of 30 multiple-choice questions. The instrument was modified by the researcher and some of the items in the PAT were adopted from previous West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) senior School Certificate Examination past questions based on the Physics contents taught in the study. Teachers' Instructional Guides (TIG) are different instructional guides uniformly used by the groups to teach the content so that the teachers would not deviate from the procedures as outlined by the researcher. The instructional guides are designed as control for the research assistant to effect. These guides were given to the experts in the Physics department, Science Educators in Science and Technology Education department and practicing senior Physics teachers for the corrections and observations. These guides consisted of notes of lesson in which the major roles of individuals participating in the study (research assistant and students) were clearly stated. Specific in the notes of lesson are the following items: subject, class, topic, instructional materials, objectives to be achieved, previous knowledge, presentation and assessment.

Instructional Procedure:

a) Instructional Procedure for Experimental Group I (Predict-Observe-Explain Strategy)

Step 1: Introduction

Activity i: Arouse students' interest and motivates them to learn by probing into their prior knowledge through questioning

Activity ii: Makes known to the students the teaching technique and its demand on them

Activity iii: Divides the students into groups of 4-7 ask them to assume the role of captain, recorder, time -keeper and so on

Activity iv: Introduces the experiment to the students

Step 2: Prediction

Activity i: students attempt individual predictions of the outcome of the experiment

Activity ii: Students write down their predictions on a sheet of paper or a prediction sheet based on the experiment

Step 3: Observation

Activity i: Instruct the students to carry out the laboratory activities

Activity ii: students record their observation

Step 4: Explaining the Observation

Activity i: The teacher asks the students to write out their explanation for their observation on the Predict-Observe-Explain worksheet

Activity ii: The students compare individual explanations and collectively brainstorm to come out with group explanation to observation

Activity iii: Teacher goes round the various groups to supervise the activities

Activity iv: teacher engages the students to correlate their prediction with their observations

Step 5: Summary

Activity i: The teacher summarizes the important points of the topic on the board

Activity ii: students copy the important points into their notebooks

Step 6: Assignment

Students are given take-home assignment

b) Instructional Procedure for Control Group (Conventional Learning Strategy)**Step 1: Introduction**

Activity i: The teacher writes the topic on the board

Activity ii: The teacher asks questions requesting information on their prior knowledge of the topic.

Activity iii: The students respond to the questions asked by the teacher.

Activity iv: The teacher establishes a link between their appropriate responses and the lesson for the day.

Step 2: Presentation

Activity i: The teacher describes/defines/ explains the new concept for the day to students.

Activity ii: The teacher demonstrates to the students the processes of each concept

Activity iii: The students observe teacher's demonstration and make comments on their observations.

Step 3: Evaluation

Activity i: The teacher examines students on the concepts taught.

Step 4: Summary

Activity i: The teacher dictated the note to the students for them to copy

Step 5: Assignment

Activity i: The students are given take-home assignments against next lesson.

The following time schedule was adopted for the process:

- The first week for the training of research assistant
- One week for pre-test
- Five weeks for carrying out the treatment
- One week for post-test

The procedure for data analysis in this study involved the use of descriptive and inferential statistics. Frequency and percentage are the descriptive statistics used for the study to show socio-demographic characteristics of the participants. The hypothesis formulated was analyzed using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) with pre-test scores as covariates. The analysis was done at 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion of Findings

Demographic Data Analysis

Table 1: Distribution of the Participants by Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	70	42.2
Female	96	57.8
Total	166	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 reveals that seventy (70) (42.5%) of the participants were males, while ninety-six (96) (57.8%) were females. This means that, most of the participants were females.

Table 2: Distribution of the Participants by Age

Age	Frequency	Percent
12-14 years	59	35.5
15-16 years	94	56.6
17 years and above	13	7.8
Total	166	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 reveals that fifty-nine (59) (35.5%) of the participants were in the age range of 12-14 years, ninety-four (94) (56.6%) were between 15-16 years, while thirteen (13) (7.8%) were 17 years and above. This means that, most of the participants were in the age range of 15-16 years, while the participants who were over 17 years were the least.

Table 3: Distribution of the Participants by Groups

Treatment Groups	Frequency	Percent
Predict-Observe-Explain (Experimental Group 1)	75	45.2
Control Group	91	54.8
Total	166	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 3 reveals that forty (75) (45.2 %) of the participants were exposed to Predict-Observe-Explain, while ninety-one (91) (54.8%) participants were in control group. This means that, many of the participants were in control group, compare to participants exposed to Predict-Observe- Explain strategy.

Hypothesis

There is no significant main effect of Predict-Observe-Explain strategy on students' achievement in Simple Harmonic Motion in Physics in secondary schools in Ogun State.

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance of Main Effect of Predict-Observe-Explain Strategy on Students’ Achievement in Simple Harmonic Motion in Physics

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	8694.278	2	4347.139	346.357	0.000	0.844
Intercept	5501.730	1	5501.730	438.349	0.000	0.774
Pretest	1.277	1	1.277	0.102	0.750	0.001
Treatment	8570.010	1	8570.010	682.814	0.000*	0.842
Error	1606.531	128	12.551			
Total	39926.000	131				
Corrected Total	10300.809	130				

Source: Field Survey, 2024 * denotes significance at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 4 shows that there was a significant main effect of Predict-Observe-Explain strategy (treatment) on students’ achievement in Simple Harmonic Motion in Physics in secondary school in Ogun State ($F_{(1,128)}=682.814, p<0.05, \text{partial } \eta^2=0.842$). The null hypothesis was therefore rejected. This implies that the treatment was effective on students’ achievement in Simple Harmonic Motion in Physics in secondary school in Ogun State. Also, the partial eta square value of 0.842 shows the contributing effect size of 84.2%.

Table 5: Estimated Marginal Means of Predict-Observe-Explain Strategy on Students’ Achievement in Simple Harmonic Motion in Physics

Treatment Groups	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Predict-Observe-Explain Strategy	27.345	0.564	26.230	28.460
Control	9.629	0.372	8.892	10.365

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 5 shows that participants exposed to Predict-Observe-Explain Strategy (treatment group) had higher posttest mean (\bar{x}) score of 27.345 on students’ achievement in Simple Harmonic Motion in Physics in secondary school in Ogun State, than their counterparts in the control group with posttest mean score of 9.629. This means that participants exposed to Predict-Observe-Explain Strategy (treatment group) performed better than those in the control group. It implies that Predict-Observe-Explain Strategy was an effective approach that improved students’ achievement in Simple Harmonic Motion in Physics in secondary schools in Ogun State.

Discussion of findings

The finding showed significant effect of Predict-Observe-Explain strategy on students’ achievement in Physics. The learners in the Predict-Observe-Explain group performed simple and specific tasks to clarify their conceptions and make some intellectual guesses about the lesson topic, therefore, the Predict-Observe-Explain instructional strategy proved better than the conventional teaching strategy. These tasks and guesses include: predicting the outcome of an event, justifying your predictions, observing a real-life event, and explaining their observations. Specifically, learners were required to perform the activities, identify their preconceptions, take responsibility for, and identify any misconceptions and correct them. As a result of these

intellectual guesses, learners were able to be more involved and responsible learners in the classroom by contributing to what the teacher taught instead of being passive listeners. Therefore, the process of teaching-learning was centered on learners.

As a result of the roles learners played, their self-confidence developed, which removed barriers of inferiority complexes among them, especially when handling apparatus and equipment. They were also empowered to take responsibility for their own learning. Learning resulted in overall improvements in learners' abilities to perform better in the practical activities they participated in during the lesson as a result of their roles in Predict-Observe-Explain Instructional strategy.

Additionally, learners' better performance was due to the fact that Predict-Observe-Explain Instructional strategy uses a deductive method of reasoning drawn from prediction, otherwise known as generalizations to observations. The reason for this is that learners' prior knowledge was revealed through their predictions, and they were accountable for those predictions based on the explanations provided. The accuracy of the predictions was confirmed by putting them to the test through hands-on activities, including conducting laboratory experiments according to instructions. It is entirely the learners' obligation to decide for themselves whether or not to accept their initial predictions. This strategy allowed them to take complete ownership of recognizing any pre-conceived notions or misunderstandings they held, leading to the correction of said misunderstandings. In essence, their learning was improved and made permanent, and their potential was realized.

The finding corroborated earlier findings of the effect of POE strategy on the Chemistry achievement of secondary school students (Erdem & Uyanik, 2022). The finding also agrees with the finding of the effects of Predict-Observe-Explain instructional strategy on students' practical skills in Physics which reported that POE was more effective than conventional method of teaching for high school students in Physics (Ojo & Owolabi, 2021).

The participants were involved in the process of learning, they felt, touched, arranged and perform experiments during the treatment period. A plausible reason for this outcome might be due to the fact that students exposed to Predict-Observe-Explain strategy participated actively in the learning process than the conventional group. Active engagement helps the students to construct knowledge and organize information into meaningful schema (Ktoridou, Doukanari & Eteokleous, 2020). Thus, when learners are actively involved in the process of learning, they construct new information from their existing mental framework for meaningful learning to occur either through the process of accommodation or assimilation (Yannier, Hudson, Koedinger, Hirsh-Pasek, Golinkoff, Munakata, Doebel, Schwartz, Deslauriers, McCarty, Callaghan, Theobald, Freeman, Cooper & Brownell, 2021). This is in line with one of the principles of learning that says students learn well when they are actively involved in the learning process (Blinkoff, Nesbitt, Golinkoff, Pasek, 2023)

Conclusion

This study investigated the effects of Predict-Observe-Explain strategy on secondary school Physics students' achievement in Simple Harmonic Motion in Ogun State. The instructional strategy that was employed in this study emphasized the participation and active intellectual involvement of students. This learner centered activity-based strategy (Predict-Observe-Explain) proved better than the conventional method. This study concluded that Predict-Observe-Explain instructional strategy enhanced students' performance in Physics.

Recommendation

1. It is important to train secondary school Physics teachers on how to use the Predict-Observe-Explain strategy to improve the teaching of Physics.
2. Predict-Observe -Explain strategy should be adopted by Physics teachers so as to correct the pre-conceived notion of students about the concept (Simple Harmonic Motion).
3. Physics topics especially, abstract concepts should be taught by associating them with the daily life of the students using simple demonstrations, class activities, team work, and home-work among others.
4. Federal, State and Local Government should upgrade the infrastructures and equip laboratories in order for the students to be actively involved in their learning.
5. Teacher education programme in Nigerian tertiary institutions should be improved upon to prepare teachers who can apply innovative approached (Predict-Observe-Explain which will promote effective teaching and learning.

References

- Acosta, L.C. (2020). Development and Assessment of Self-paced Module for Grade 7 Science cum Worksheets, *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications (IJSRP)*, 10(7), 8-23
- Adebayo, F., & Olufunke, B.T. (2015). Generative and Predict-Observe-Explain Instructional Strategies: Towards Enhancing Basic Science Practical Skills of Lower Primary School Pupils, *International Journal of Elementary Education*, 4(4), 86-92
- Adonu, C.J., Nwagbo, C.R., Ugwuanyi, C.S., & Okeke, I.O. (2021). Improving Students Achievement and Retention in Biology Using Flipped Classroom and Power-point Instructional Approaches, Implication for Physics teaching, *International Journal of Psychological Rehabilitation*, 25(2), 234-247
- Agbele, A.T. Oyelade, E. A. & Oluwatuyi, V.S. (2020). Assessment of Students' Performance in Physics using Two Teaching Techniques, *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*, 7(7), 55-59
- Akbar M. & Budiarti, I.S. (2021). Analysis of Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTs) on Simple Harmonic Motion Concept Using Virtual Laboratory Based on VBA Excel Study in Physics Education Students of Universitas Cenderawasih, 2nd International Conference on Education and Technology (ICE TECH), 81-89
- Ali, P.A. (2023). Factors affecting Quality and Effective Practical Work in Senior Secondary School Physics in Ebonyi State of Nigeria, *Ebonyi State College of Education, Ikwo, Journal of Educational Research*, 8(2), 56-60
- Al-Khalili, J. (2020). *The World According to Physics*, Princeton University Press, , 25-35
- Arslan, M., & Irfan, E.M., (2020). The Effect of Predict-observe-explain Strategy on Students' Academic Achievement, Scientific Process Skills and Attitude toward Science, *Inonu Universitesi Egitim Bilimleri Enstitusu Dergisi*, 7(14), 79-89
- Arziqulogli, E. J. & Iixomovich, T. M. (2022). Deduction Method of Teaching Exact Sciences, *Central Asian Journal of Mathematical Theory and Computer Science*, 3 (10), 23-29
- Assem, H.D., Nartey, L., Appiah, E., & Aidoo, J.K. (2023). A Review of Students' Academic Performance, Misconceptions and Teachers Qualification, *European Journal of Education and Pedagogy*, 4(1), 84-92

- Barut, D., & Cibik, A. (2022). The Effect of POE Activities Supported by Concept Networks on Laboratory Attitudes, Anxieties and Scientific Process Skills of Pre-service Science Teachers, Hacettepe Universites Egitim Facultesi Dergisi, Hacettepe *University Journal of Education*, 37(4), 123-129
- Bastos, J.C., Sales, G.L., & Monteiro, J.A. (2021). Object of Learning in the Teaching of Simple Harmonic Motion: a case Study Using Active Methodology (ISLE type), *Research, Society and Development*, 10(14), 122101-421137
- Blinkoff, E. T., Nesbitt, K., Golinkoff, R. M., Pasek, K. H. (2023). Investigating the Contributions of Active, Playful Learning to Student Interest and Educational Outcomes, *Acta Psychologica*, 238, 2023,103-983
- Busari, G.A. (2023). Interactive-lecture Demonstrations and Guided-reverse Jigsaw Instructional Strategies and Secondary School Students Learning Outcomes in Concepts of Light in Physics in Oyo-state, Nigeria, 52-54 (Doctoral Thesis)
- Darmaji, D., Kurniawan D. A. & Irdianti, I. (2019). Physics Education Students' Science Process Skills, *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 8(2), 293-298
- Dennis, J.L., & Somerville, M.P. (2022). Supporting Thinking about Thinking: Examining the Metacognition Theory, Practice Gap in Higher Education, *Higher Education*, 1-19
- Duygu, Ç., & Halil, İ. Y. (2020) The Effect of Prediction, Observation, Explanation Supported Project-Based Environmental Education on the Levels of Attitude and Behavior Toward the Environment, *Educational Policy Analysis and Strategic Research*, 15(1), 23-25
- Edoja A. E. & Gbadamosi, O. (2020). Raising the Achievement and Retention levels of Secondary School Students in Physics through Brain-Based Learning strategy in Taraba State, Nigeria, *BSU Journal of Science, Mathematics and Computer Education*, 1(2), 87-97
- Efgivia, M.G., Adora, R.R., Suriyam, H.A., Maulana, I., & Budiarjo, A. (2021). Analysis of Constructivism Learning Theory, Proceedings of the 1st UMGESHIC International Seminar on Health, Social Science and Humanities,10
- Engin, G. (2020). An Examination of Primary School Students Academic Achievements and Motivation, Teacher Self-efficacy and Leadership Approach, *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 16(1), 257-276
- Erdem, O.G. & Uyanik, G. (2022). The Effects of the Academic Achievement, Attitude and Retention in Science Learning, *Journal of Pedagogical Research*, 6(3), 103-111
- Erdem, O.G., & Uyanik, G. (2022). The Effects of the Academic Achievement, Attitude and Retention in Science Learning, *Journal of Pedagogical Research*, 6(3), 103-111
- Falode, O.C. Francis, O.R. Micheal, F.B., & Dennis, O.O. (2020). Examining the Novelty, Interactivity and User-friendly Attributes of Virtual laboratory Package for Conducting Nigerian Secondary School Physics Experiments, *Journal of Science Education*, 25-30
- Gulbin, O. & Topsakal, U.U. (2021). Investigating the Effectiveness of STEM Education on Students' Conceptual Understanding of Force and Energy Topics, *Research in Science and Technology Education*, 39(4), 441-460
- Gulejova B.B. & IPPOG (2021). Collaboration, Bridging the Gap between Science Education at School and Modern Scientific Research, in GRIBOV-90 Memorial Volume, Field Theory, Symmetry and Related Topics, Proceedings of the Memorial Workshop Devoted to the 90th Birthday of VN, Gribov, 91-113

- Hartanto, T.J., Santoso B., & Frianto, Z. (2024). The Effect of Flipped Classroom Learning Assisted by Computer Simulation on Students' Comprehension of Simple Harmonic Motion, *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan IPA*, 10(4), 1950-1960
- Islamiyah, K.K., Rahayu, S., & Dasna, I.W. (2022). The Effectiveness of Remediation Learning Strategy in Reducing Misconception on Chemistry, A Systematic Review, *Tadris J. Kegur.dan Ilmu Tarb*, 7(1), 63-77
- Kane S.A. & Gelman B.A. (2020). Introduction to Physics in Modern Medicine, CRC Press, 2020, 4-7
- Kieuoanh, P.T., & Hongnhung, N.T. (2022). Constructivism Learning Theory: A Paradigm for Teaching and Learning English in Secondary Education in Vietnam, *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publication*, 82-88
- Kilipamwambu, S.T. (2021). Teachers' Perceived Difference between Content and Competence Based Curricula in Secondary School, A case of Dares Salaam Region, PhD Thesis, the Open University of Tanzania, 25-28
- Knapp, N. F. (2019). The Shape Activity, Social Constructivism in the Psychology Classroom, *Teaching of Psychology*, 46(1), 87-91
- Ktoridou, D., Doukanari, E., & Eteokleous, N. (2020). Fostering Meaningful Learning Experiences through Student Engagement. IGI Global. (Eds.), 25-45
- Kurniawan, M.A., Rahayu, S. Fajaroh, F., & Almuntasher, S. (2020). Effectiveness of Dual Situated Learning Model in Improving High School Students' Conceptions of Chemistry Equilibrium and Preventing their Misconceptions, *Journal of Science and Learning*, 3(2), 99-105
- Mao, P., Cai, Z., He, J. Chen, X., & Fan, X. (2021). The Relationship between Attitude towards Science and Academic Achievement in Science, A three-level Meta-analysis, *Frontiers in Psychology* 12, 23-30
- Marx, E., Leonhardt, T., & Bergher, N. (2023). Secondary School Students' Mental Models and Attitudes regarding Artificial Intelligence-A scoping review, *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 100-169
- Ne. A., & An, A. (2020). Computer Simulation Model Effect on Students' Academic Achievement in Computer Logic, *International Journal of Management*, 11 (8), 2020, 122-129
- Novitra, F. (2021). Development of Online-Based Inquiry Learning Model to Improve 21st-Century Skills of Physics Students in Senior High School, *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 17(9), 25-28
- Ocheni, C.A. (2024) Test Anxiety and Academic Stress as Predictors of Secondary School Students Academic Achievement in Physics, PhD Thesis, University of Nigeria, Nsukka
- Ojo, O. M. & Owolabi, O. T. (2021). Effects of Predict-Observe-Explain Instructional Strategy on Students' Learning Outcomes in Physics Practical in Secondary Schools, *European Journal of Education Studies* 8(2), 152-159
- Ojo, O. M., & Owolabi, O. T. (2020). Effects of Predict-Observe-Explain and Virtual Laboratory Instructional Strategies on Secondary School Students' Performance in Physics Practical, *European International Journal of Science and Technology* 9(1), 1-3
- Pacala, F.A. (2023). Simple Harmonic Oscillating Using Computer Simulation: Compilation of Experiments for Classroom Investigation, *EDUCATUM Journal of Science, Mathematics and Technology*, 10(1), 80-89

- Pacela, F.A. (2023). Simple Harmonic Oscillation Using Computer Simulation, Compilation of Experiments for Classroom Investigations, *Education Journal of Science, Mathematics and Technology*, 10 (1), 80-89
- Pulana, A.D. (2022). Motivational Strategies of Teachers in Relation to Learners' Academic Performance, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Analysis*, 125-130
- Ramdayami, R., Latifah, K.M., Yurniwati, Y., & Taofik, T. (2023) Innovative Strategies in Science Education: Implementing the POE Model to Enhance Elementary School Students' Science Process Skills, *Jurnal Pendidikan Sains*, 12(1), 25-37
- Roger, M.M. (2020). Examining the Benefits of Teaching Active Study Strategies as a part of Classroom Instruction, *International Journal of Innovative Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, 1(2), 41-55
- Selin, A. & Kaya, E. (2020). How do University Students Perceive the Nature of Science? *Science Education* 29(2), 299-330
- Sidik, R., Mulyaningsih, N.N., & Astuti, I.A. (2021). Development of Predict-Observe-Explain (POE)-Based Physics Module by Utilizing QR Code and You Tube Learning Videos, *Nucleus*, 2(2), 54-61
- Soechoarto, S., Csapo, B. Sarimanah, Dervi F.I., & Sabri, T. (2019). A Review of Students' Common Misconceptions in Science and their Diagnostic Assessment Tools, *Jurnal Pendidikan IPA, Indonesia*, 8(2), 247-266
- Thomas, C.G. (2021). *Research Methodology and Scientific Writing*, Springer Cham, 2nd Edition, 45-76
- Umam, A. & Sukarmin S. (2020). Using two-tier Based Concept Test to analysis Profile of Student Understanding on the Concept of Simple Harmonic Motion, *Journal of Physics, Conference Series*, 15-20
- Usman, I.S., Simvyap W.L., & Fasanya, A.G. (2019). Challenges of Effective Implementation of New Secondary School Physics Curriculum in Public and Private Schools in Nigeria, *ATBU Journal of Science, Technology and Education*, 7(3), 1-6
- Venida, A.C., & Sigma, E.M. (2020). Predict-Observe-Explain Strategy, Effects on Students' Achievement and Attitude toward Physics, *Journal Pendidikan MIPA*, 21(1), 78-94
- WAEC (2015-2018). Chief Examiners' Reports
- WAEC (2019). Chief Examiner's Report, 25-29
- Yannier, N., Hudson, S.E., Koedinger, K., Hirsh-Pasek, K., Golinkoff, R.M., Munakata, Y., Doebel, S., Schwartz, D. L., Deslauriers, L., McCarty, L.S., Callaghan, K, E.J., Theobald, Freeman, S., Cooper, K.M., & Brownell, S.E.(2021). Active Learning: "Hands-on" meets "minds-on", *Science*, 374, 26 - 30.
- Yulianti, R., Suhandi, A., & Sopandi, W. (2020). The Effect of POE Strategy on Students' Conceptual Change regarding Water Density, *Journal Pendidikan Sekolah Dasar*, 6(1), 15-29